

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF TENTH STANDARD GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE SCHOOL STUDENTS IN SOCIAL SCIENCE CURRICULUM: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Abstract:

The aim of the study is to compare the academic achievement of X Standard government and private school students in Social Science curriculum. A sample of 425 government school and 425 private school X Standard students from Thanjavur, Kumbakonam and Pattukkottai Educational Districts were chosen using Simple Random Sampling method. Academic Achievement Test in Social Science (AATSS) developed and standardized by the investigator was used for collecting data and the data were statistically analysed. The results revealed significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science; Significant difference was found with regard to boys, girls and rural school X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science but not with urban school students.

Key Words: Academic Achievement, Government and Private School Students & Social Science Curriculum

Introduction:

Success leads to success. A success is a win over a competing phenomenon and eventually is an achievement. The sense of achievement brings Joy, happiness, successful feeling and enthusiasm to everyone which stands as an influencing factor for further actions and efforts (Sudhakar & Nellaiyapen, 2016) for everyone. Academic achievement is one of the basic expectations and has been attracting credentials from all and at all levels. 'Academic' the adjectival term refers to those activities related to studies in learning context, be it formal or informal. Academic achievement has been within the purview of the student community. Students have to achieve and yet 'student achievement' or 'academic achievement of students' has exalted or troubled all the teachers, on the ground that teachers are primarily responsible for students' achievement. The facilities available in the school, the nature of school, the individual differences among the students, the non-supportive learning environment at home or of parents, the affecting socio-economic factors are not considered when a student's academic achievement becomes low or poor. In this context, this research investigation aims at comparing government and private school X standard students' academic achievement in Social Science.

Review of Related Literature:

Sudhakar & Nellaiyapen (2016) investigated relationship between academic achievement and parent-child relationship of high school students. The results revealed that the level of academic achievement was average and parent-child relationship of high school students was extreme cordial. There was a significant relationship between the academic achievement and parent-child relationship of high school students.

Thornton (2015) examined parental involvement in the education of primary school students in a poverty stricken, low-income community in Chicago. The study showed the majority of parents were involved in the education of their students and showed low confidence in parent involvement. The results showed room for improvement for parent teacher relationships and parental involvement.

Emmanuel, Adom, Josephine, & Solomon (2014) found significant correlation between self-concept and academic achievement in Mathematics Test among the X Standard students of China.

Bostani, Nadri & Nasab (2014) concluded that the higher the mental health of the students, the better their educational performance.

Kaur (2013) established the significant correlation between academic achievement in relation to achievement motivation of X Standard high school students of Punjab.

Lacour & Tissington (2011) studied the effects of poverty on academic achievement and found out that poverty significantly affected the resources available to students. Due to this lack of resources, many students struggled to reach the same academic achievement levels of students not living in poverty. The factors affecting student achievement include income, source of income, and mother's education level.

Amrai, Motlagh, Zalani, Parhon (2011) confirmed the existence of positive and significant correlation between academic motivation and academic achievement among Tehran University students.

Muola (2010) affirmed significant positive relationship between six of the home environmental factors, that is fathers' occupation, mothers' occupation, fathers' education, mothers' education, family size and learning facilities at home and academic achievement motivation among Standard Eight pupils in Kenya.

Significance of the Study:

In deciding the future academic career of a student at an early stage, X Standard plays a role of greater importance. It is on the basis of the marks scored, a major criterion that decides the academic achievement, the students are admitted in the higher secondary course. The Secondary School Leaving Certificate (S.S.L.C.) Mark Sheet includes Social Science as one of the subjects and any student of X Standard has to score the minimum pass marks, or else the student would be declared fail. No doubt, academic achievement in Social Science too becomes valuable and significant contributor in deciding the further continuance of studies.

The nature of government schools, its administrative style, the available infra-structure facilities, the co-operation of the teachers and students, the background of the students, the parental involvement and the other learner-affecting factors are not the same as private schools. It is the opinion of the common man that private schools are better and private school students excel better than the government school students and so the growing admissions in private schools and the decline in government schools. The investigator is interested in finding out the difference, if there is, scientifically by a comparative study. The findings of the study would be helpful to excel in his profession personally and of great contribution to the entire student community of X Standard, believes the investigator. The transferability "the degree to which the results of qualitative research can be generalized or transferred to other contexts or settings" (Trochim, 2006) of this study will be more as this study has been conducted on a large sample size from three educational districts. Hence, the study is significant.

The investigator, being a Teacher Trainee who had selected Geography, a major component of Social Science subject, in his graduation and post-graduation studies, has

a special interest and affinity, to pursue research in this subject. In this research, he has attempted to make a comparative study of academic achievement of X Standard government and private school students in Social Science curriculum.

Statement of the Problem:

“A Comparative Study of Academic Achievement of X Standard Government and Private School Students in Social Science Curriculum”.

Operational Definitions:

Comparative Study:

In the study, it refers to the comparison of academic achievement of X Standard government and private school students.

Academic Achievement:

In the study, it refers to the marks scored by the X Standard students in the Academic Achievement Test in Social Science conducted by the investigator.

Social Science Curriculum:

It refers to the content of the Social Science Textbook prepared by the Government of Tamil Nadu for the X Standard students.

Government Schools:

It refers to the government schools and government aided schools.

Private Schools:

It refers to the schools run by private organizations without getting grant-in-aid from the government.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to boys.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to girls.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to rural school.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to urban school.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to nature of the school.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- ✓ There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to boys.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to girls.

- ✓ There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to rural schools.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to urban schools.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to nature of schools.

Delimitations of the Study:

Considering the time, resources available and feasibility, the investigator has delimited the study to the following areas:

- ✓ The study is delimited to the X Standard students only.
- ✓ The sample size is delimited to 850 students only.
- ✓ The study is carried out only in the three Educational Districts of Thanjavur, Kumbakonam and Pattukkottai only.
- ✓ Academic Achievement Test in Social Science conducted by the investigator and the secured marks alone decides the academic achievement.

Methodology, Population and Sample of the Study:

Survey Method was adopted for the study. "Researchers make the distinction between a population, the universe of people to which the study could be generalized, and a sample, the subset of people from the population who will participate in the current study" (Vanderstoep & Johnston. 2009, p.26). In the study, all the X Standard students studying in Thanjavur, Pattukkottai and Kumbakonam Educational Districts form the population. The randomly selected 425 government school students and government-aided Schools students, and 425 private school students of X Standard, and altogether 850 students, form the sample in the study.

Tool Description and Data Collection:

The tool developed and standardized by the investigator and the guide (2015) 'Academic Achievement Test in Social Science' was used in the study. A preliminary draft tool, with 90 multiple choice question items with four options, was prepared. After revision and establishing the content validity, 'Pilot Study' was conducted on 150 sample (75 government school students & 75 private school students) selected randomly from the 4 schools of Thanjavur, Kumbakonam and Pattukkottai Education Districts. Based on statistically calculated 'Difficulty Index Value' and 'Discriminative Power Value' of 'Item Analysis' process, 18 items were deleted and 72 items were selected for the final study. The score value of one was given for the correct answers responses and zero for the wrong answers. The investigator directly administered the test and collected data from 850 sample and data were statistically analysed.

Statistical Treatment:

The collected data using 'Achievement Test in Social Science' were subjected to the following statistical treatment:

- ✓ Mean
- ✓ Standard Deviation
- ✓ t-test

Hypotheses Testing:

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science.

Table 1: Difference between X Standard Government and Private School Students in their Academic Achievement in Social Science

Category	N	Mean	S.D.	Calculated 't' value	Significant/ Not Significant
Government School Students	425	63.56	18.664	6.10	Significant
Private School Students	425	56.05	19.584		

It is inferred from the table 1 that the calculated 't' value (6.10) is greater than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 % level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, the result shows that there is significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science. While comparing the mean scores of the government school (Mean value=63.56) and private school (Mean value=56.05) X Standard students, the government school students are better than the private school students in their academic achievement.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to boys.

Table 2: Difference between X Standard Government and Private School Students in their Academic Achievement in Social Science with regard to Boys

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	Calculated 't' value	Significant/ Not Significant
Government School Boys	200	68.29	15.454	6.84	Significant
Private School Boys	225	56.56	19.330		

It is inferred from the table 2 that the calculated 't' value (6.84) is greater than the table value (1.96) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, the result shows that there is significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to boys. While comparing the mean scores of government school boys (Mean value=68.29) and private school boys (Mean value=56.56), the government school X Standard boys are better than the private school X standard boys in their academic achievement in Social Science.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to girls.

Table 3: Difference between X Standard Government and Private School Students in their Academic Achievement in Social Science with regard to Girls

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	Calculated 't' value	Significant/ Not Significant
Government School Girls	225	59.37	20.240	1.99	Significant
Private School Girls	200	55.48	19.899		

It is inferred from the table 3 that the calculated 't' value (1.99) is greater than the table value (1.96) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, the result shows that there is significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to girls. While comparing the mean scores of government school girls (Mean value=59.37) and private school girls (Mean value=55.48), the government school X Standard girls are better than the private school X Standard girls in their academic achievement in Social Science.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to rural school.

Table 4: Difference between X Standard Government and Private School Students in their Academic Achievement in Social Science with regard to Rural Schools

Locality of School	N	Mean	S.D.	Calculated 't' value	Significant/ Not Significant
Government Rural School	215	67.93	16.066	7.62	Significant
Private Rural School	210	55.03	18.745		

It is inferred from the table 4 that the calculated 't' value (7.62) is greater than the table value (1.96) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, the result shows that there is significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to rural schools. While comparing the mean scores of government rural schools (Mean value=67.93) and private rural schools (Mean value=55.03), the government rural school X Standard students are better than the private rural school X Standard students in their academic achievement in Social Science.

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to urban schools.

Table 5: Difference between X Standard Government and Private School Students in their Academic Achievement in Social Science with regard to Urban Schools

Locality of School	N	Mean	S.D.	Calculated 't' value	Significant/ Not Significant
Government Urban Schools	210	59.10	20.069	1.04	Not Significant
Private Urban Schools	215	57.05	20.365		

It is inferred from the table 5 that the calculated 't' value (1.04) is less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, the result shows that there is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to urban schools.

Hypothesis 6: There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to nature of the schools: (a) Boys' school, (b) Girls' school and (c) Co-education schools.

Table 6: Difference between X Standard Government and Private School Students in their Academic Achievement in Social Science with regard to Nature of the School

Nature of the School	School	N	Mean	S.D.	Calculated 't' Value	Significant/ Not Significant
(a) Boys' School	Government	100	73.84	12.051	7.69	Significant
	Private	110	56.50	19.375		
(b) Girls' School	Government	115	62.79	17.354	2.88	Significant
	Private	110	55.74	19.319		
(c) Co-ed. School	Government	210	59.10	20.069	1.58	Not Significant
	Private	205	55.99	19.924		

It is inferred from the table 6 that the calculated 't' value for (a) Boys' schools (7.69) is greater than the table value (1.96) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis (a) Boys' schools is rejected. Thus, the result shows that

there is significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to boys' school. While comparing the mean scores of government boys' school (Mean value=73.84) and private boys' school (Mean=56.50), the government boys' school X Standard students is better than the private boys school X standard students in their academic achievement in Social Science.

The calculated 't' value for (b) Girls' schools (2.88) is greater than the table value (1.96) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis (b) Girls' schools is rejected. Thus, the result shows that there is significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to girls' school. While comparing the mean scores of government girls' schools (Mean value=62.79) and private girls' school (Mean value=55.74), the government girls' school X Standard students is better than the private Girls' school X standard students in their academic achievement in Social Science.

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value for (c) Co-education schools (1.58) is less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis (c) is accepted. Thus, the result shows that there is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to Co-education schools.

Findings of the Study:

- ✓ There is significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science.
- ✓ There is significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to boys.
- ✓ There is significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to girls.
- ✓ There is significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to rural schools.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to urban schools.
- ✓ There is significant difference between X Standard government and private school students in their academic achievement in Social Science with regard to (a) Boys' school and (b) Girls' school but not with (c) Co-education schools.

Conclusion:

There is a range of factors that affect the quality of performance of students (Waters & Marzano, 2006). The background of the students studying in government schools and private schools varies a lot and eventually their academic achievement too would have to. The finding that the X Standard students studying in government schools do better in Social Science than the private school students is an eye-opener and a credit. It is an appreciation to the intensive efforts taken by the government and government aided schools in the recent years and will motivate the teachers to teach with more vigour and enthusiasm in par with private schools in the years ahead.

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